

Work Life Balance Of Working Women In Education Sector : A Case Study Of Naushahro Feroze And Mirpurkhas

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ABSTRACT

This paper talks about work life balance of working women in education sector particular in District Naushahro Feroze and MirpurKhas WLB is important topic in academic and business practices, women has to satisfy their work and their family which has to positive impact on work life balance. WLB is measured by psychological distress scale, work satisfaction scale and family satisfaction scale, researcher apply the quantitative research and numerical analysis of the data using the random sampling method taking only female working women which works in education sector ,and filled the survey questionnaires data from District Naushahro Feroze and MirpurKhas 's private and government schools, universities campuses, and colleges. That was analyzed through IBM SPSS 16.0 check questionnaires scales validity through Chronbach's Alpha that is (0.994), of 160 returned questionnaires out of 200. Than co-relation has to be used for hypothesis proving and see relationship between variables. This study also identifies main problems and challenges which faced by married working women.

INTRODUCTION

Work Life Balance is a term which means to balance the work (ambition and career) and style of living (family, hobbies, health and leisure). Initially centuries women were engaging and working at their home cleaning and kitchen only some of them has job and engaged in education sectors, industries, social works, and little firms, little ratio of women are gets the higher literacy and advanced education which are to be directed at the pity of their parents and grooms, behavior towards women life and work. The quickly evolving knowledge parsimony has taken place for most number of ratio of women can be refined by higher literacy. Education is not only allow women for gets knowledge but it also helps them to booming their careers with their brain power in this competitive worlds, rather than suffering , female employees sound to drift in lot of factories education sectors and industries on parity with men. but it became a tough time and big challenge for all women because she has to be faced the duties and responsibilities of homes as well as offices. When working women comes in form of marital status their responsibilities more increase and again when she will be mother than ultimately their duties will be enlarged, because they must be care of their children as well as look after their home and family too under very big stress to be walk on their career line. Today's working mothers are busy and engaged to perform their family duties and also focus on their careers to handle challengeable claim of their various roles. Children caring, home responsibilities and duties that working mother have secular a very big pressure on that when she will incorporated with their office duties and professional life. The struggle of working women to co-ordinate, construct and harmony the different issues and moments to their various roles as one puts under terrible burden.

Life balance of work is most common in various field like in behavioral science, (Allan, Loudoun & Peetz, 2007), people and employee management (Grady, McCarthy, Darcy & Kirrane, 2008; McDonald, Pini & Bradley,2007 , psychology / mental make-up (Greenhaus, 2008; Frone, 2000), gender specific studies (Sullivan & Smithson, 2007; Hill, 2005; Sullivan & Lewis, 2001) & firms studies (Kelly, Kossek, Hammer, Durham, Bray, Chermack, Murphy & Kaskubar, 2008). A lot of women are working in colleges, schools, private centers, with lowest salaries in early ages, as effect women feel compel to work long hours for giving security of their jobs, due to promptly changing in business conditions, companies cannot be handover secure employment and for that reason the values, job satisfaction, attitudes, norms of employees are also change (Guest, 2002) .

Family Circle modulation that affected on the work life balance of women as individual basis, in current days it is include women working at different palaces and increasing the household work too, as earlier concept is also follow still today that women are homemaker, it means they are engaging in their home cleaning, food preparation, baby caring, and handle all conflicts which are occurs in family and work, (Falkenberg and Monachello, 1990; Ramu, 1989). So that working women plays double role.

1.1 Research Aim:

The theme of research is to identify the different factors which will affects on work life balances of working women, like as; working hours, work family conflict, psychological distress, work satisfaction, family satisfaction, family responsibilities, children caring, office duties, career building, job involvement also focus that how married working women maintains their family and husband duties and if she will became mother how she will manage their office work, spouse duties and children caring.

1.2 Statement of the problem:

In Naushahro Feroze, and MirpurKhas there are so many working women which are working in education sector researcher wants to find out that how they live their lives and make it balance, researcher also wants to determine the important reasons of poor work life balance between working women of education sector includes working hours, overtimes, traveling from their homes to schools / colleges / university campuses, negative attitudes from their families, negative attitudes from their bosses and supervisors, also household works and loss of working agenda.

1.3 Research Objectives:

- To identify the challenges faced by married working women.
- To identify major problems of work life balance with single and married working women with respect to their demographic factors like as age, occupation, marital status, qualification.
- To identify different factors which affect work life balance of working women from educational sector
- To examine more occurring factors which influence on the working women

1.4 Hypothesis:

H1 = Work Life balance is positively significant with family satisfaction.

H2= Work Life balance is positively significant with work satisfaction.

H3=Work Life balance is positively affected on psychological stress.

1.5 Research Methodologies:

Researcher goes for quantitative research because that gives more accurate facts and figures. For the data collection researcher goes for survey with questionnaires mainly in three districts of Sindh by use random sampling method with sample size of 90 and 30 sample of women taken from each district's colleges, schools and university campuses.

1.6 Limitations:

This research posses various limitations. First that is return backing of questionnaires, which researcher distributes to working women in two districts out of 200 questionnaires only 160 returned back, researcher could not go for all districts of Sindh and all working sectors due to shortage of time researcher has specifically gathered data only from two district's education sector which are listed below:

- Naushahro Feroze
- MirpirKhas.

Another limitation is that mostly data is to be taken from private schools and majority ratio of women in private schools is single in marital status. Participants have limited time, though some of them not read questionnaires properly just gives answers, even they can't understand that what were asked by researcher.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Life adjust of work is general term, which is clarified in unmistakable structures by modified specialists working diverse measurements. The topic of research on life adjust of work can be essentially scratched to request on ladies/female have various parts.

Life adjust of work is clarified as a ladies worker's reasoning that few tenets of family mind, proficient, individual life, and work which are kept up with low level of contention (Clark, 2000; Ungerson and Yeandle, 2005). Equalization of work life is a critical issue in whole classifications of work as twofold vocation families turns out to be more broad and gigantic work necessities with deference elevated working hours have transform into a lead/design. Critical thing is that the working ladies must be keep up adjust between their work necessities and home lives. Likewise observe the statistic changes that part of ladies are working in numerous areas and

has have twofold vocation families that is increment disparate workforce and a higher obligation of that ladies representatives to adjust their work and non-work lives (Bharat, 2003; Komarraju, 1997; Rajadhyaksha and Bhatnagar, 2000; Ramu, 1989; Sekharan, 1992). Work Life adjust issues are intense and there is need of lessening that with entry of time. The contention are emerges in the middle of work and family and that contention has strong deposit. It truly influences the estimation of family/individual life and in addition working/profession life satisfaction of ladies and also men as well. (Friedman and Greenhaus 2000). There are part of issues are emerges of work life adjust so for the arrangements of that issues "worker amicable associations orchestrated and created Work life adjust programs in particular alludes (WLBP's). Work Life Balance programs are to discover for raise representative supervision and work put (Thomas and Ganster, 1995) and subtracted strife which emerges amongst family and work (Kossek and Ozeki, 1998) and pressure (Thompson and Prottas, 2006).

Work-life adjust is critical for individuals' success, affiliations' execution additionally, a working society (Grady et al., 2008). There are unmistakable feelings on how function life adjust should be described, measured and asked about (Grzywacz and Carlson, 2007). Particular terms are furthermore used by different researchers while implying 'work-life equality'. For example, Frone (2003), Greenhaus et al. (2003) and Clark (2000) suggest the term 'work-family modify'; Clarke et al. (2004) insinuate 'work-family fit'; Burke (2000) suggests 'work-singular life adjust'; and Grady et al. (2008) imply 'work-life leveling'. As work-family adjust is as often as possible associated with standard families, i.e., individuals who are hitch with youths (Barnett and Hyde, 2001), and this examination insinuates a family in the two its standard and non-regular structure; remembering the ultimate objective to along these lines keep up a key separation from any perplexity the term 'work-life adjust' is used all through this paper. Grady et al. (2008, p.3) express that the term 'work-life adjust' is more careful and joins "family, gathering, entertainment and individual time". As communicated by Grady et al. (2008) WLB in its wide sense gets all parts of delegates' up close and personal and work life; this prescribes WLB should be based on individuals, families, workplaces, gatherings, and society with everything taken into account. Nevertheless, due to word number and time limits, this examination maintained a strategic distance from gathering and societal viewpoints, and focused on individuals, families and workplaces. The written work exhibits different WLB definitions. For instance, Clark (2000, p.751) depicts WLB as "satisfaction and extraordinary working at work and at home, with at any rate part battle". Clarke et al. (2004, p.121) express that WLB is an "adjust or keeping up general sentiment understanding in life". Greenhaus et al. (2003, p.511) describe WLB as "the measure of time and the level of satisfaction with the work and family part". Frone (2003, p.145) presents a four-crease logical grouping of work-life balance, in which WLB is depicted as "low levels between part battle and raised measures of between part help". Grzywacz and Carlson (2007, p.458) assume that WLB is an "accomplishment of part related wants that are orchestrated and shared between an individual and his/her part related assistants in the work and family spaces". A couple of theories have been proposed by researchers to clear up WLB. Clark (2000) showed an edge theory as demonstrated by which family and work zones are detached by borders which could be physical, momentary or mental. A couple of authorities (e.g. Edwards and Rothbard, 2000; Lambert, 1990) implied pay theory as showed by which workers endeavor to find greater satisfaction in one territory to compensate for the nonattendance of satisfaction in the other space. Others (e.g. Rothbard and Dumas, 2006; Grzywacz and Marks, 2000) imply flood theory as demonstrated by which any opinions, emotions, mindsets and practices delivered in one space can be traded or 'flooded' into the other range. Frone (2003) and Grzywacz and Marks (2000) proposed more hypothetical models where WLB can be measured by work-family and family work strife and what's more work-family and family-work change. Grzywacz likewise, Marks (2000) executed Bronfenbrenner's organic model which proposes that work-family encounter is a joint capacity of process, individual, time and setting qualities, and does not limit the experience to either negative or positive (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Clark (2000) clarifies that emphasis on the areas of work and family is fundamental, as family and work are the most vital components of everybody's life. Any contending requests of work and family life will cause struggle and adversely influence the prosperity of laborers (Clark, 2000; Frone, 2000). Clarke et al. (2004) and Clark (2000) concur that quantifiable parts of WLB are fulfillment, absence of part strife and a general feeling of concordance. Greenhaus et al. (2003) trust that harmony amongst family and work areas likewise includes time adjust, association adjust, and fulfillment adjust. Frone (2003) states that the quantifiable four parts of the harmony amongst work and family parts are: (a) work-family struggle, (b) family-work strife, (c) work-family improvement, and (d) family-work upgrade. As these segments have bi-directional impacts on Work life adjust (Frone, 2003; Grzywacz and Marks, 2000; Frone et al., 1992; Greenhaus and Beutell, 1985).

2.1 Demographic changes and Work Life Balance:

A decades ago some time recently, statistic insurgency like as. ladies are taking part in workforce places, twofold pay families, might be parent/single family, and changed as result issues are to be expanded which are looked by those ladies laborers, which will be make adjust of their family and work life (Tennant and Sperry, 2003; Young, 1999) . Work-family battle happens when work practices interfere with family works out, moreover, strangely, family-work strife happens when family practices intrude with work works out (Breugh and Frye, 2007; Hill, 2005). The composition shows distinctive implications of work-family battle and family-work strife. Netemeyer, Boles and McMurrian (1996, p. 401) delineate family-work battle as "a kind of cover part battle in which general

solicitations of, time focused on, and strain made by the family interfere with performing business related commitments", besides, work-family battle as "a sort of bury part strife in which the general solicitations of, time focused on, and strain made by the occupation intrude with performing family-related commitments". Research has shown that work-family battle and family-work strife are a delayed consequence of weight made by incongruent work and family parts (Yang, 2005; Greenhaus and Beutell, 1985). Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) battle that enthusiasm for the work space is more troublesome in light of collaboration in the family space, and the a different way. Greenhaus and Beutell (1985, p.77) describe work family and family-work conflicts as "a kind of disintegration in which part weights from work and family spaces are generally opposite in a couple of respects". These conflicts happen bi-directionally, which suggests that a negative inclusion with work can impact agents' family life, and the a different way, (Carlson and Kacmar, 2007; Yang, 2005). This occurs in light of the fact that work-family strife is antagonistically related to family life satisfaction, while family-work strife is related with bring down work satisfaction (Frone, 2003; Williams and Allinger, 1994). As demonstrated by Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) there are three sorts of work-family strife and family-work battle: (a) period based conflict, (b) strain-based strife, and (c) direct based conflict. Time-based conflict rises where business related activities or family-related activities battle with various activities (Yang, 2005). Strain-based conflict happens when weights and demands of one section battle with the solicitations of the other part (Edwards and Rothbard, 2000). Direct based conflict rises when lead expected in one section conflicts with that typical in the other part (Edwards and Rothbard, 2000). Numerous scientists agree that work-family strife and family-work battle are oppositely related to family life satisfaction and work satisfaction (e.g. Parasuraman and Greenhaus, 2002; Allen, Herst, Bruck and Sutton, 2000; Netemeyer et al., 1996), and thusly are unfavorably related to WLB (Kalliath and Monroe, 2009). A couple of researchers demonstrate various conditions and final products of work-family battle and family-work strife. These revelations don't for the most part accomplish similar conclusions. For example, Allan et al. (2007) found that an over the top workload has a more grounded negative impact on work-family strife than long working hours, while Major, Klein and Ehrhart (2002) found a positive

2.5 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

DEPENDENT VARIABLE

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

The aim of this research to see how women make balance of their work life and their personal life which are working women in education sector and also find out the different factors which affects on work life balance of working women. Researcher use quantitative methods for the data collection.

Choice of Research Method:

Researcher is going to use of quantitative method for the data collection because quantitative gives authentic results as compare to qualitative method, Quantitative research based on Survey & self completion questions (Close Ended questions / open ended question) in that respondents can give the answers absence of data collector/ researcher/ interviewer (Saunders et al ; 2012 ; Collis & Hussey, 2009)

Description Of Sample:

Reason for sampling is only that to select subset of particular from entire population to measure the components of entire population (Collis & Hussey, 2009; Fisher, 2007). Simple Random Sampling method is used for collection of data, taken 160 samples of working women, and they all are from education sector, from above mentioned three districts, taken equal half samples from each district. This study also relies on too focused on single, married and mothers which are working in education sector.

Participants:

Researcher selects those participants which are working as full time in different private schools, government schools, government colleges and university campuses mainly in two districts Naushahro Feroze, and MirpurKhas. Taking those female employees which are single, married and mothers who live with their children. The 160 sample of respondents is consists only female (100%) in which the age range started from 19-55.

Questionnaire Design:

Questionnaires are designed for data collection that distributed among participants/respondents, where they respond for same set of questions in fixed structure (deVas 2002). Questionnaires are attached in Appendix (I) .Questionnaires is designed according to the factors is suppressed of 24 close-ended questions and divided in five parts mainly they are consists on (1) Demographic (2) work life balance (3) Family Satisfaction (4) Work Satisfaction and (5) Psychological Distress that are used to measure the Work Life Balance, first 12 questions are according to their demographic, tabular effect questions used for measuring work life balance, next five questionnaires used to measure the family satisfaction scale, after that five questionnaires for work satisfaction and in last eight likert scale questions from psychological distress factor that construct for the working women which are working in education sector . In demographic questionnaires research use multiple choice question method but in other factors questionnaires researcher use the likert scale method. Respondents can tick any option with respect the distinct factors according to their preference. Questionnaires are in English language, and quiet much easy and simple which are easily understandable by all women.

Implementation Of Research

Researcher collects the data dated between 1-09-2016 till 15-10-2016 from different working women of schools, colleges, and university campuses. Total 200 questionnaires are handed to women majority target group are married women, and single women and mothers. After the completion of data researcher going to analysis that data by using of SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) Software 16.0 version and MS- EXCEL 2007

Research Analysis

The major theme of this study to see the factors which are affecting on work life balance of working women. Three major factors were to be identified which are directly affected to Work Life Balance. In this chapter researcher go for analyzing of the data and interpret their results regards data which collected from various working women from different districts. Above Researcher finds most accruing factors of work life balance of working women in education sector that are family satisfaction, work satisfaction, and psychological distress. Three hypotheses are designed for this study that are tested through correlation analysis for checking relationship among variables, for hypothesis testing initially researcher measure the validity and reliability through chronbach's alpha in each variable.

4.1 Reliability Test :

4.1.1 Reliability Test between all variables:

Researcher put all data in SPSS conducted the reliability test through the chronbach's alpha it's one of the tool to measure the internal consistency that how set of items are closely related with each other, here researcher check out the validity of all likert type of

questionnaires which possess the above given factors, eighteen questionnaires possess likert type of scale , data results are (0.994) which is acceptable and posses excellent level of their internal consistency of selected sample table is mentioned below:

Table 1 (Reliability Test through Chronbach’s Alpha)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.994	.994	18

4.1.2 Reliability Test of Family Satisfaction Scale

Table 2 (Reliability Test of Family Satisfaction Scale)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.990	.990	5

Above table represents the reliability of family satisfaction scale the value is (0.990) 99%, shows that there is excellent internal consistency in that scale.

4.1.3 Reliability Test of Work Satisfaction Scale

Table 3 (Reliability Test of Work Satisfaction)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.989	.990	5

Table represents the reliability of work satisfaction scale the value is (0.989) 98.9%, shows that there is excellent internal consistency in that work satisfaction scale.

4.1.4 Reliability Test of Psychological Distress Scale

Table 4 (Reliability Test of Psychological Distress)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.988	.990	8

Above table represents the reliability of psychological distress scale the value is (0.988) 98.8%, which shows that there is excellent internal consistency in that scale.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics:

Researcher shows their results of demographic questions in Descriptive Statistics which used to classifying, presenting and summarizing of primary collected data, what the data which was collected that data present through frequency distribution, measures of central tendencies, measures of dispersion, as well as graphical representation like as ; Bar Charts, Histograms, Pie Charts, Polygon, Dot Plots (Pallant, 2013).. Here researcher shows frequency distribution and pie charts of demographic questions like as, working women ratio, age factors, qualifications, motivation that they are working in working in education sectors, dependency rates that in home how many people are depends on there’s salaries, than it shows mean, standard deviation.

4.2.1 Age Of Respondents:

Table 5 (Frequency Distribution Table Of Ages of Respondents)

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-30	90	56.2	56.2	56.2
	31-40	31	19.4	19.4	75.6
	41-50	23	14.4	14.4	90.0
	51-60	16	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total		160	100.0	100.0	

Figure 1 (Pie Chart of Ages of Respondents)

According to survey above graph is showing that highest ratio of respondents are between 20-30, (56.2%) and the lowest ratio of respondents are 51-60 age (10%), as well as moderate ratio are respondents are 31-40 (19.4%) and 41-50 (14.4%) mostly younger’s women are working in the education sector.

4.2.2 Marital Status Of Respondents:

Table 6 (Frequency Distribution Table of Marital Status of Respondents)

Marital status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	81	50.6	50.6	50.6
	Married	77	48.1	48.1	98.8
	Divorced	2	1.2	1.2	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

Figure 2 (Pie Cart Of Marital Status of Respondents)

According to findings and study it shows that majority of respondents in sample were Single working women 81 in quantity (50.6%) , married women were 77 in quantity (48.1%) and minority ratio of respondents were divorced 2 in quantity (1.2%). Mostly in private schools single marital status ratio was too high & in government schools finds the senior teachers they all were married; only two of them were divorced.

4.2.3 Qualification Of Respondents:

Table 7 (Frequency Distribution Table of Qualification of Respondents)

Qualification

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bachlors	78	48.8	48.8	48.8
	Masters	68	42.5	42.5	91.2
	Diploma	6	3.8	3.8	95.0
	PHD	6	3.8	3.8	98.8
	M.phil	2	1.2	1.2	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

Figure 3 (Pie Cart of Qualification of Respondents)

Above frequency distribution tables reflects the qualifications of respondents in that highest ratio of respondents comes in bachelors which are 78 in quantity (48.8%), (42.5%) 68 respondents are comes in Masters (3.8%) 6 comes in Doctorate and (3.8%) 6 comes in Diploma holders and only (1.2%) 2 respondents have done M.phill degree. PHD and M.phill holders mainly finds in colleges of Naushahro Feroze and Mirpurkhas , while bachelors holders find in private Schools and masters holders were there find in government schools as well as Sindh university MirpurKhas Campus and Sindh University Naushahro Feroze Campus.

4.2.4 Dependency rate of their family members Of Respondents:

Table 8 (Frequency Distribution Of Dependency Rate of their family members)

Dependency Rate					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	42	26.2	26.2	26.2
	2	42	26.2	26.2	52.5
	3	28	17.5	17.5	70.0
	4	26	16.2	16.2	86.2
	5	18	11.2	11.2	97.5
	6	2	1.2	1.2	98.8
	7	2	1.2	1.2	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4 (Pie Cart of Dependency Rate)

Above frequency distribution table and pie chart clearly reflects about the dependency rate that women which are working in education sectors how much family members depends upon that, highest ratio reflects that 42 women respond that they have only one family member (26.2%), than again 42 women respond that they have two family members depend upon their salaries (26.2%), 28 women (17.5%) respond that they three members depend upon that, 26 women (16.2%) replied that four members are depends upon that, 18 women (11.2%) respond that five family members rely on that, finally lowest ratio reflects that two working women (1.2%) respond that six family members rely on that also two women (1.2%) respond that seven members depend upon that.

4.2.5 Occupation / Designation Of Respondents:

Table 9 (Frequency Distribution of Occupation / Designation)

		Designation			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	School Teacher	94	58.8	58.8	58.8
	Lecturer	36	22.5	22.5	81.2
	Visiting Faculty	7	4.4	4.4	85.6
	Research Associate	10	6.2	6.2	91.9
	Assistant Professors	6	3.8	3.8	95.6
	Lab Assistant	5	3.1	3.1	98.8
	Professor	2	1.2	1.2	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5 (Pie Cart of Occupation of respondents)

Above tables describe the occupation of respondents highest sample was School teachers 94 (58.8%), because very high ratio of private and government schools in Naushahro Feroze and MirpurKhas although in every city too, than 36 (22.5%) lecturers were found mostly in Colleges, 10 (6.2%) of them were Research Associates, 7 (4.4%) were Visiting Faculty members, they all found in Sindh University Naushahro Feroze Campus, 6 (3.8%) were Associate Professors, 2 (1.2%) Professors were professors got lower ratio and mainly they found in Sindh University MirpurKhas Campus, and 5 (3.1%) are Lab Assistants.

4.2.6 Employment Status Of Respondents :

Table 10 (Frequency Distribution of Employment Status)

		Employment Status			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Full time	130	81.2	81.2	81.2
	Part time	20	12.5	12.5	93.8
	Casual	10	6.2	6.2	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

Figure 6 (Pie Cart of Employment Status)

Above Frequency Distribution table reflect the employment status of respondents, out of 160 sample size highest ratio goes to full time , 130 (81.2%) respondents shows that they have their full time jobs , because mostly in government schools, and colleges employees works full time basis that starts from 9.AM till 2. PM, than 20 (12.5%) of them have Part time jobs because they are engage in studies as well as their do jobs too, 10 (6.2%) of them have casual jobs they work as visiting faculties in Sindh University and Shaheed Benazir University Campus Naushahro Feroze and MirpurKhas.

4.2.7 Feel that work hours is fit your personal life

Table 11 (Frequency Distribution of Work Satisfaction with Personal Life)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly DisSatisfied	3	1.9	1.9	1.9
DisSatisfied	6	3.8	3.8	5.6
Neutral	8	5.0	5.0	10.6
Satisfied	86	53.8	53.8	64.4
Strongly DisSatisfied	57	35.6	35.6	100.0
Total	160	100.0	100.0	

Figure 7 (Pie Chart of Work Satisfaction with Personal Life)

Frequency Distribution shows the statement “women employees were satisfied with work and personal life” from above statement mostly women were satisfied 86 (53.8%) that they are feel that their working hours are fit with their personal lives because school and college teachers jobs and classes started from 9. AM till 2.PM, they all prepare their breakfast and than be ready for schools / colleges than up to 2.PM they come back to their homes so that’s why they can make their lunch and do some other work too. 57 (35.6%) are strongly satisfied, 8 (5%) women respond that nor satisfied nor dissatisfied they don’t say anything, regards this statement, only 6 respondents (3.8%) dissatisfied with this statement lowest ratio is 3 (1.9%) of them were strongly dissatisfied because there is problems with married working women which are work as visiting faculties, and work as part time because they face their studies and their job too that’s why only few of them are disagree.

4.2.8 Able to balance work and life

Table 12 (Frequency Distribution of Able to balance work and life)

Able to balance of Work Life

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	143	89.4	89.4	89.4
No	17	10.6	10.6	100.0
Total	160	100.0	100.0	

Figure 8 (Pie Chart of Able to Work Life Balance)

This is one of dichotomous type of question which has only two options yes or no, so researcher wants to know that working women life is balance or not? From the above frequency distribution table it is clearly shows that highest ratio ranked 143 women (89.4%) says that they make balanced their work life and their family life because in education sector job have specific time period that start from 9.Am till 2 Pm that’s why women have make balanced of their lives, 17 (10.6%) ratio mothers working women which has child their lives were not balanced.

4.2.9 Time Spending on domestic Activities:

Table 13 (Frequency Distribution Of time spending on home activities)

Time spending on domestic activities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 2 hours	24	15.0	15.0	15.0
	2-4 hours	58	36.2	36.2	51.2
	4-6 hours	28	17.5	17.5	68.8
	more than 6 hours	50	31.2	31.2	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

Figure 9 (Pie Chart Of time spending on home activities)

Above frequency distribution table reflects that time spending on domestic / home activities , highest ratio tells us 58 women mainly (36.2%) ratio is spending two to four hours in their home activities because married working women who wake up early in the morning than go for working in schools/colleges from morning till noon she becomes too tired than fulfill home responsibilities so they do not have enough time to engage in extra domestic activities, than 50 single working women mainly (31.2%) ratio spend more than six hours in home activities, 28 (17.5%) respond that they spend four to six hours, in the activities, lowest ratio tells that 24 women (15%) spending their life in domestic activities.

4.2.10 Work for long hours even overtime :

Table 14 (Frequency Distribution Table Work for long hours even overtime)

Do you work long even overtime

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Frequently	22	13.8	13.8	13.8
	Sometimes	62	38.8	38.8	52.5
	Occasionally	13	8.1	8.1	60.6
	Rarely	17	10.6	10.6	71.2
	Never	46	28.8	28.8	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

WORK FOR LONG HOURS EVEN OVERTIME

Figure 10 (Pie Chart of WORK FOR LONG HOURS EVEN OVERTIME)

Above frequency table represents that working women work for long hours even overtime, extra timing, so highest ratio goes to 62 respondents (38.8%) respond that sometimes, they work as overtime second ratio is about never 46 respondents (28.8%) respond that they never mostly married working has look after their children, so they don't have do much time for overtime, frequently 22 (13.8%) work as overtime basis, 17 (10.6%) respondents respond that rarely they work as overtime basis, 13 women (8.1%) work overtime as occasionally basis.

4.2.11 Due to Pressure of work miss out quality time with family and friends

Table 15 (Miss quality time due to work pressure)

Miss Quality Time due to Work Pressure

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Frequently	19	11.9	11.9	11.9
Sometimes	69	43.1	43.1	55.0
Occasionally	12	7.5	7.5	62.5
Rarely	19	11.9	11.9	74.4
Never	41	25.6	25.6	100.0
Total	160	100.0	100.0	

MISS QUALITY OF TIME DUE TO WORK PRESSURE

Figure 11 (Pie Chart of Miss quality time due to work pressure)

Above frequency distribution reflects that due to pressure of work women miss out the quality time with their family and friends, highest ratio of respondent’s 69 (43.1%) shows that sometimes they, miss their quality timing, because they engage their work life in schools, colleges, and university campuses, they work 5 to 6 hours over there, 19 respondents (11.9%) shows that frequently they miss the time, 41 respondents (25.6%) respond that they have no work pressure and never miss the quality timings, 12 (7.5%) reflects that occasionally they miss it, and 19 (11.9%) of them responds that rarely they miss that.

4.2.12 Factors for work motivation

Table 16 (Frequency Distribution Table of factors for work motivation)

		Motivate you to work			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Personal Satisfaction	79	49.4	49.4	49.4
	Finanacial Independence	44	27.5	27.5	76.9
	Support from family	37	23.1	23.1	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

Figure 12 (Pie chart of factors for work motivation)

Above frequency distribution talks about the factors being a working women which factor motivates you for the work, when researcher meets with different working women in private schools and colleges highest ratio respond that they work only for giving personal satisfaction to themselves, 79 respondents rate (49.4%) , than 44 women (27.5%) respond that they work only for financial independence, some women has issue regards finance mostly in private sectors single working women 20-30 age group we were found when we ask this question they replied that they belongs very poor family they don’t have strong financial background so that’s why they join private schools for being financial independence lowest ratio is 37 respondents (23.1%) they respond that they work because they have support from their families.

4.3 Mean And Standard Deviation :

Researcher computed the mean scores and standard deviation of all factors.

4.3.1 Mean And Standard Deviation Of Family Satisfaction Scale:

Mean Scores and standard deviation is mentioned below of each family satisfaction scale which posses likert scale questionnaires (rely on answers of participants).

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
There isn't much time to socialize/relax with my partner/see family in the week	3.09	1.568	160
Relaxing and forgetting about work issues is hard to do	3.19	1.489	160
My relationship with my partner is suffering because of the pressure or long hours of my work	2.58	1.576	160
My family are missing out on my input, either because I don't see enough of them/am too tired	3.22	1.549	160
Finding time for hobbies, leisure activities, or to maintain friendships and extended family relationships is difficult	3.28	1.445	160

Table 18 (Mean Scores of Family Satisfaction Scale)

From above table highest mean “Finding time for hobbies, leisure activities or to maintain the friendships and extended family relationships is difficult” which mean score is (3.28) the married working women don’t have too much time for their hobbies like exercising, chatting / to give the time to their friend and it really tough to maintain the friendships, The next statement is “My family members are missing out because I don’t see enough of them I am too tired due to work pressure” has (3.22) mean score working women mostly busy in their work so that’s why she don’t gives too much time to their family and when she come back from the work mostly she wants to be take some rest, (3.19) mean in the statement “Relaxing and forgetting about work issue is hard to do?” , Due to pressure of the work sometimes it’s hard to remember everything their stress level is high so they were worry about their health too. Here is another mean scores (3.09) “There isn’t much time to socialize /relax with my partner” mostly this problem faced by married working women which works in colleges and university campuses due to work projects ,assignments they don’t have too much time for giving to their partner. And last mean score is (2.58) “My relationship with my partner is suffering due to work pressure or long hours of my work” because in Pakistan due to inflation when husband and wife both are working than family can be running, so that’s why this statement is not too much effect to working women.

4.3.2 Mean And Standard Deviation Of Work Satisfaction Scale:

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
At the moment, because the job demands it, I usually work long hours	2.97	1.631	160
I have to take work home most evenings	3.64	1.535	160
I often work late or at weekends to deal with paperwork without interruptions	3.07	1.488	160
I worry about the effect of work stress on my health	3.20	1.678	160
I would like to reduce my working hours and stress levels, but feel I have no control over the current situation	3.46	1.613	160

Table 19 (Mean Scores of Work Satisfaction Scale)

In above table Highest mean score (3.64) got the statement “I have to take work home most in evenings” because in morning time working women be prepare school / college / university so that’s why she take their work in house and done in evening time, the second highest mean score (3.46) statement is “I would like to reduce their working hours an stress level but I felt that I have no control on that” mother working women / those who have child has lot of anxiety, frustration, tenseness with respect of their children so their stress level is increased, “I worry about the effect of work stress on my health” statement got (3.20) mean score women has too much burden of the work specially single working women who works in private schools ,they has lot of work they check fair copies , assignments, children projects, makes new innovative practices for children “I often work late or at weekends to deal with paper work without interruptions” this statement has (3.07) mean score , and last mean score got (2.97) “ At the moment, because the job demand it, I usually work long hours”. This statement not supported to because working women in education sectors have limited time (5 hours) started from 9.AM to 2.PM to performing their duty so they don’t usually work as long hours.

4.3.3 Mean and Standard Deviation of Psychological Distress Scale:

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
I am satisfied with my leisure/free hours	160	4.31	1.041
I am happy to get nice sleep of 8 hours at night	160	4.11	1.221
I am satisfied with family trip, enjoying vacation	160	4.08	1.358
I am satisfied to my weekend shopping and outing	160	3.60	1.489
I am satisfied about sparing quality time with family	160	3.96	1.251
I can celebrate events and birthdays with family	160	3.86	1.348
I have satisfaction with the exercise I undergo every day	160	3.38	1.491
I am satisfied about spending time for my self	160	3.86	1.414
Valid N (listwise)	160		

Table 20 (Mean Scores of Psychological Distress Scale)

Above table shows that the mean scores and standard deviations of psychological distress factor the first statement “I am satisfied with my leisure hours/ free hours” got highest mean scores (4.31) women were mostly strongly agree from this statement the next statement “I am happy to get nice sleep of 8 hours at night” got (4.11) mean score in education sector working ladies works from 9. Am till 2.Pm than they maintain their family work after that she can sleep well women teachers are also satisfied with family trip, and enjoying vacation this statement got (4.08) mean score, in education sectors there are two months summer vacations which is in June and July, and also last days of December month so they can enjoyed with family trips and tours, after this statement “I am satisfied about sparing quality time with my family” has got (3.96) mean score, she also giving some only few time to their family due to pressure of work, there is equal mean scores (3.86) of “I am satisfied about spending time for myself” and “ I can celebrate events and birthdays with my family” both statements shows interconnectivity with each other. The next statement “I am satisfying to my weekend shopping and outing” there is no any availability of public parks or any other spot for visiting where women can come for reducing of their stress level, Lowest mean score (3.38) got this statement “I have satisfaction with the exercise I undergo every day” women of Mirpurkhas and Naushahro Feroze not refers exercise early at morning.

4.4 CORRELATION ANALYSIS:

		W L B	Fam_Satis	Wrk_Sats	Psy_Strs
W_L_B	Pearson Correlation	1	.954**	.920**	.809**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	160	160	160	160
Fam_Satis	Pearson Correlation	.954**	1	.987**	.904**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	160	160	160	160
Wrk_Sats	Pearson Correlation	.920**	.987**	1	.938**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	160	160	160	160
Psy_Strs	Pearson Correlation	.809**	.904**	.938**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	160	160	160	160

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 21 (Correlation among variables)

In this study proposed three hypotheses so proving of that hypothesis researcher applied correlation test (r), it is one of the part of inferential statistics to determine the strength of relationship between (work life balance “dependent variable”) (family satisfaction, work satisfaction, psychological distress “independent variables”) how these four variables relates with each other. Pallant (2013) tells that researcher apply the co-relation to see the relationship between dependent variable and independent variable, whether it is positive / negative (Cohen 1988) suggests that if $P < 0.05$ it is reach significance. Co-relation values range from -1.00 to +1.00. if the value is 0.01 to 0.25 it shows, weak but positive co-relation, the value from 0.25 to 0.50 shows that moderate positive co-relation, 0.50 to 0.75 shows that strong positive co-relation and if value is 1.00 than it means that variables are perfectly positively co-related, when value is 0 it means there is no, co-relation between variables, same like if value If value is in – it shows negative relationships like as if value is -0.01 to -0.25 it shows weak negative relationship, the value between -0.25 to -0.50 that shows that moderate negative relationship, if values comes -0.50 to -0.75 than it states that strong negative relation finally when value is -1.000 it reflects that there is perfect negative co-relation. Researcher used simple bivariate co-relation in SPSS 16.0 version, for showing the strength of relationships in between variables.

4.5 HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Hypothesis one states that work life balance is positively significant to family satisfaction in order to see the relationship in between work life balance measure through (Work Life balance questionnaires) and family satisfaction measured through (family satisfaction scale questionnaires) both were checked through Pearson’s co-efficient Co-relation. The value is ($r=0.954$) $p < 0.01$ it means there is strong co-relation between work life balance and family satisfaction, that is supported first hypothesis

Hypothesis two states that work life balance is positively significant to work satisfaction in order to see the relationship in between work life balance measure through (Work Life balance questionnaires) and work satisfaction measured through (work satisfaction scale questionnaires) both were checked through Pearson’s co-efficient Co-relation. The value is ($r=0.920$) $p < 0.01$ it means there is strong co-relation between work life balance and work satisfaction, that is supported second hypothesis

Hypothesis three states that work life balance is positively significant to psychological distress in order to see the relationship in between work life balance measure through (Work Life balance questionnaires) and psychological distress measured through (psychological distress scale questionnaires) both were checked through Pearson’s co-efficient Co-relation. The value is ($r=0.809$) $p < 0.01$ it means there is strong co-relation between work life balance and family satisfaction, that is supported third hypothesis.

CONCLUSION This study is conducted to measure the work life balance of working women in education sector of Naushahro feroze and Mirpurkhas in modern era it is very important to know that how women satisfy their work and also maintain effective relationship with their family so there is need to systematic research. This research has to be conformed that work life balance is positively significant to family satisfaction, work satisfaction and psychological distress; even co-relation statistically significant has also proved and supported argument. Day by day women are increasing in workplaces. This study showed that major problems occurs with married working women that are work hours, overtime, traveling from home which is less important for women, negative attitude from supervisor, negative attitude from family and major problem is household work has to be identified in this research because women who works in their schools, colleges and university campuses they have too much burden of their responsibilities, so that’s why they feel becomes more stress, anxiety, pressurize, they can’t give appropriate time to household work .

Women plays dual role they work in their home as well as, in their offices too, single working women mostly works in private schools, and they feel lot of burden of their work i.e. checking fair copies, assignments, home projects, home works of students so that's why they take their work in homes and mostly done in evenings time.

Above study also prove that it's tough for mother working women to balance their family and work life irrespective they work in any sector, because they faced lot of hurdles, child development, child education, family work conflict and work family conflict can arises which affects the health of working women, so they become more stressful, than start headache's, creates lot of tension, and feel disturb than their male correspondent.

Today's world is busy everyone is engaging in the work women don't have too much time to give concentration on their health, surely it said that wellbeing programs and health caring programs can help for balancing their personal and working life.

REFERENCES

- i. Allan, C., Loudoun, R. & Peetz, D. (2007) 'Influences on work/non-work conflict'. *Journal of Sociology*, 43 (3): 219-239.
- ii. Bharat, S. 2003. "Women, work, and family in urban India, Towards new families?" in J. W. Berry, R. C. Mishra, and R. C. Tripathi ed., *Psychology in human and social development, Lessons from diverse cultures pp.155-169* New Delhi, India, Sage.
- iii. Breaugh, J. A. & Frye, N. K. (2007) 'An examination of the antecedents and consequences of the use of family-friendly benefits'. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 19 (1): 35-52.
- iv. Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979) *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- v. Brough, P., O'Driscoll, M. & Kalliath, T.J. (2005) 'The ability of family friendly organizational resources to predict work-family conflict and job and family satisfaction'. *Stress and Health*, 21(2): 223-234.
- vi. Clark SC (2000). *Work/Family Border Theory: A New Theory of Work/Family Balance*. *Human Relations* 53(6): 747-770.
- vii. Cohen, J.W. (1988) *Statistical power analysis for the behavioural sciences* (2nd ed). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- viii. Collis, J. & Hussey, R. (2009) *Business Research: A Practical Guide for Undergraduate and Postgraduate Students* (3rd ed). Hampshire: Macmillan Publisher Ltd.
- ix. Diener, E., Emmons, R.A., Larsen, R.J. & Griffin, S. (1985). 'The Satisfaction with Life Scale'. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 49: 71-75.
- x. DeVaus, D.A. (2002) *Surveys in Social Research* (5th ed). London: Routledge.
- xi. Edwards, J. R. & Rothbard, N. P. (2000) 'Mechanisms linking work and family: Clarifying the relationship between work and family constructs'. *Academy of Management Review*, 25 (1): 178-199.
- xii. Frone, M. R. (2003) 'Work-family balance'. In: Quick, J.C. & Tetrick, L.E. (eds). *Handbook of occupational health psychology*. Washington: American Psychological Association, 143-162.
- xiii. Friedman, S D and Greenhaus, J H (2000). "Work and family—Allies or enemies? What happens when business professionals confront life choices", New York: Oxford University Press.
- xiv. Greenhaus, J. H. & Beutell, N. J. (1985) 'Sources of conflict between work and family roles'. *Academy of Management Review*, 10 (1): 76-88.
- xv. Greenhaus, J. H., Collins, K. M. & Shaw, J. D. (2003) 'The relation between work-family balance and quality of life'. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 63 (3): 510-531.
- xvi. Greenhaus, J.H. (2008) 'Innovations in the study of the work-family interface: Introduction to the special section'. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 81: 343-8.
- xvii. Grady, G., McCarthy, A., Darcy, C. & Kirrane, M. (2008) *Work Life Balance Policies and Initiatives in Irish Organizations: A Best Practice Management*. Cork: Oak Tree Press.
- xviii. Goldberg, D. (1972) *The detection of psychiatric illness by questionnaire: A technique for the identification and assessment of non-psychotic psychiatric illness*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- xix. Kalliath, T., & Monroe, M. (2009) 'Work-life balance: A structural evaluation of its antecedents across five Anglo and Asian samples'. Paper presented at the 8th Australian Industrial and Organisational Psychology Conference, Sydney, June, 2009.
- xx. Kelly, E.L., Kossek, E.E., Hammer, L.B., Durham, M., Bray, J., Chermack, K., Murphy, L.A. & Kaskubar, D. (2008) 'Getting there from here: Research on the effects of work-family initiatives on work-family conflict and business outcomes'. *The Academy of Management Annals*, 7(2): 305-49.
- xxi. Kossek E. E. and Ozeki C. 1998. *Work-family conflict, policies, and the job-life satisfaction relationship, A review and directions for organisational behavior-human resources research*, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol.83, pp.139-149.
- xxii. Netemeyer, R.G., Boles, J.S. & McMurrian, R. (1996) 'Development and validation of work – family conflict and family – work conflict scales'. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81(4): 400-410.
- xxiii. Pallant, J (2013) *SPSS: Survival Manual* (5th ed). Berkshire: McGraw Hill.

- xxiv. Parasuraman, S. & Greenhaus, J. H. (2002) 'Toward reducing some critical gaps in work-family research'. *Human Resource Management Review*, 12: 299-312.
- xxv. Poelmans, S., O'Driscoll, M., & Beham, B. (2005) 'An overview of international research on the work-family interface'. In Poelmans, S. (eds). *Work and Family: An international research perspective*. New York: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 3-36.
- xxvi. Rothbard, N. P. & Dumas, T. L. (2006) 'Research perspectives: Managing the work-home interface'. In: Jones, F., Burke, R. & Westman, M, (eds). *Work-life balance: A psychological perspective*. New York: Psychology Press, 71-89.
- xxvii. Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2012) *Research Methods for Business Students (6th ed)*. Essex: Pearson.
- xxviii. Spector, P.E., Cooper, C.L., Poelmans, S., Allen, T.D., O'Driscoll, M., Sanchez, J.I., Siu, O.L., Dewe, P., Hart, P. & Lu, L. (2004) 'A cross-national comparative study of work-family stressors, working hours, and well-being: China and Latin America versus the Anglo world'. *Personnel Psychology*, 57:119-142.
- xxix. Sullivan, C. & Lewis, S. (2001) 'Home-based tele work, gender, and the synchronization of work and family: Perspectives of tele workers and their co-residents'. *Gender Work and Organization*, 8(2): 123-145.
- xxx. Thompson C. A. and Prottas, D. J. 2006. Relationships among organisational family support, job autonomy, perceived control, and employee well-being. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, Vol. 11, pp.100-118.
- xxxi. Thomas L.T. and Ganster D.C. 1995. Impact of family-supportive work variables on work-family conflict and strain: A control perspective. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol.80, pp.6-15.
- xxxii. Tennant, G. P. & Sperry, L. (2003) 'Work-family balance: Counselling strategies to optimise health'. *Family Journal-Counselling Therapy for Couples and Families*, 11(4): 404-408.
- xxxiii. Whaley, C. J., Morrison, D. L., Wall, T. D., Payne, R. L. & Fritschi, L. (2005) 'Chronicity of psychological strain in occupational settings and the accuracy of the General Health Questionnaire'. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 10(4): 310-319.
- xxxiv. Yang, N. (2005) 'Individualism-collectivism and work-family interface: A Sino- US comparison'. In: Poelmans, S.A.Y. (eds). *Work and family: An international research perspective*. London: Lawrence Erlbaum, 287-319.